

On the Derivation of the Kaniadakis Energy Distribution

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 6, 2020

The Maxwell-Boltzmann and Maxwell-Juttner energy distributions appear frequently in the literature. Recently, G. Kaniadakis has proposed an alternative relativistic distribution which fits certain experimental data. In (1), he first states that $A(f_1)+A(f_2) = A(f_3)+A(f_4)$ ((1)), where f is the energy distribution and A a function (the analog of the natural log for the Maxwell Boltzmann or Juttner distributions). He then uses: $d/df [f A(f)] = 1/b A(q f)$ ((2)), where b and q are to be determined, as the starting point of his theory and goes on to show $b=1/\sqrt{1-k^2}$, $q=(kb + \sqrt{1+k^2b^2})^{1/k}$ where k is determined experimentally. Furthermore, $A(f)$ is given by $1/2k (f^k - f^{-k})$ and there is also an expression for $f(e)$. In this note, we try to show Kaniadakis' results follow directly from ((1)) without need of ((2)).

The Kaniadakis Distribution

Kaniadakis (1) does not start with the standard idea:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((3))$$

(The solution for f which he obtains does not seem to satisfy ((3)) except in the classical limit in which his $f(e)$ becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.)

Kaniadakis (1) starts with the idea that there is a conservation law, for example, conservation of energy $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$.

$$A(f(e_1)) + A(f(e_2)) = A(f(e_3)) + A(f(e_4)) \quad ((4))$$

It seems that it immediately follows that $A(f)=1$ i.e. A and f are inverse functions. One pair of inverse functions is $A=\ln(f)$ and $f=\exp(-e/T)$. If e is classical, this yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, if e is relativistic, the Maxwell-Juttner. For the latter, $e=\sqrt{p^2+mo^2}+V(x)$. Actually, any pair of inverse functions satisfy ((4)), but one expects that $f(e)$ drops rapidly with increasing e . In addition, the relativistic distribution function should approach the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in the nonrelativistic limit.

In (1), Kaniadakis takes the following as the starting point of the derivation of his distribution:

$d/df [f A(f)] = 1/b A(q f)$ ((5)) where f , A are functions to be determined and b and q parameters. His results yield:

$b=1/\sqrt{1-k^2}$, $q=(kb + \sqrt{1+k^2b^2})^{1/k}$ where k is determined experimentally and

$$A(f) = 1/2k (f^k - f^{-k}) \text{ and } f(e) = \{ [\sqrt{1 + (ek/T)^2} + ke/T] \}^{1/k}$$

One may show that A and f obtained by Kaniadakis are inverse pairs i.e.

$$A(f) = 1/2k ([\sqrt{1 + (ek/T)^2} + ke/T] - 1/ [\sqrt{1 + (ek/T)^2} + ke/T]) = e/T$$

A possible problem, however, is that ((3)) does not seem to be satisfied i.e.

$f(e)f(E-e)$ is not equal to a constant.

For a nonrelativistic problem, if ((3)) is not satisfied, then a collision and its time reversed collision do not have the same probabilities. As a result, it is not clear one would have an equilibrium distribution. If one takes the limit $k \rightarrow 0$ $f(e)$ of Kaniadakis becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and ((3)) is satisfied. (In the relativistic Maxwell-Jüttner distribution ((3)) is also satisfied.)

Alternative Derivation

We argue ((5)) is not needed as the starting point for the derivation of the Kaniadakis distribution, but rather it follows from ((4)). If energy is the conserved quantity, one need only find a function and its inverse, but mathematically there may be many such results. Instead, we consider $e_3 = e_1 + de$ and $e_2 = e_4 + de$ and energy conservation: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. Next, we use ((1)) and expand. Thus:

$$f(e_1 + de) = f(e_1) + de \frac{d}{de} f(e_1) \quad ((6a)) \text{ and}$$

$$A(f(e_1) + de \frac{d}{de} f(e_1)) = A(f(e_1)) + de \frac{df}{de} \frac{d}{df} A(f) \text{ (at } e_1) \quad ((6b))$$

Then ((1)) becomes:

$$A(f(e_1)) + A(f(e_4)) + de \frac{df}{de} \frac{d}{df} A(f) \text{ (at } e_4) = A(f(e_1)) + A(f(e_4)) + de \frac{df}{de} \frac{d}{df} A(f) \text{ (at } e_1) \quad ((7))$$

This suggests that $\frac{df}{de} \frac{d}{df} A(f) \text{ (at } e_i) = \text{constant} \quad ((8))$ for any e_i . Alternatively:

$$\frac{d}{de} [A(f(e))] = \frac{d}{de} e \text{ or } \left(\frac{df}{de} \right) \left(\frac{dA}{df} \right) = 1$$

For the solution $A(f) = \ln(f)$ and $\frac{df}{de} = -1/T f$ one sees that $\frac{d}{df} A(f)$ is proportional to $1/f$ and $\frac{df}{de}$ to f . One may try to find another solution that retains this behaviour, as one ultimately wants the nonrelativistic limit of this new function to be the Maxwell-Boltzmann result.

It may be noticed that $1/f$ follows immediately from taking d/df of f^k or f^{-k} . Thus one may try a solution proportional to:

$A(f) = a/k (f^k \pm f^{-k})$ ((9)) (Here we choose - in anticipation of Kaniadakis' result. One may pursue the other option as well).

Then, $d/df A(f) = (a/f) (f^k \pm f^{-k})$ ((9))

f also has an explicit functional form based on e , the energy.

Next, consider $d/de f$ being proportional to f . We use a power type relationship which seems also inherent in the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution derivation. Thus, we try:

$f = g(e)^{1/k}$ ((10)) where $g(e)$ is unknown

$d/de f = 1/k f(e) 1/g dg/de$ ((11))

Then, $d/df A(f) = a/f (g \pm 1/g)$ and by using ((8)) we have:

$df/de d/df A(f) = \text{constant} = C = (g \pm 1/g) (1/g) dg/de$ ((12))

Let $dg/de = q(e)$ an unknown function, yielding a quadratic equation for ((12)). Thus, it seems one should look for a quadratic type solution i.e.

$g(e) = \text{sqrt}[(-d/deq) / (C - d/q/de)]$

In general, one may try to search for a solution of the most general quadratic form, namely:

$g(e) = q_1(e) \pm \text{sqrt}(q_2(e))$ ((13))

((13)) must yield a result which satisfies ((12)). One may show that:

$g(e) = (\text{sqrt}(1 + (ek/T)^2) + ke/T)$ ((14)) suffices. Here we introduce $1/T$ as e is divided by temperature in the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Juttner cases.

One may also show that A defined by ((9)) and f are inverse functions, as already show in section (1).

Thus, one is able to obtain the Kaniadakis distribution directly from ((1)) basically by looking for a function, inverse function pair and using some properties of the derivatives of \ln and $\exp(-ax)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to show the Kaniadakis distribution follows directly from a conservation equation $A(f(e_1)) + A(f(e_2)) = A(f(e_3)) + A(f(e_4))$ where energy e_i is conserved. In such a case, one seeks a function A such that f is its inverse. In the nonrelativistic limit, the result should yield the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. It seems, however, that the Kaniadakis $f(e)$ does not satisfy ((3)) which is needed for equilibrium. In the nonrelativistic limit, however, ((3)) is satisfied. For the Maxwell-Juttner distribution ((3)) is satisfied in the relativistic region.

References

Kaniadakis, G. Relativistic Kinetics and Power-Tailed Distributions. 2010

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/48169936_Relativistic_kinetics_and_power-law_tailed_distributions